

FEATURES OF PERSONAL DEVELOPMENT OF A WEIGHTLIFTER

Kholmuratov Fayzullo Hayitovich

Termez State University

Lecturer at the Department of Sports Management

Annotation. The article is devoted to the socio-psychological understanding of weightlifting, which is an important factor in the development of an athlete's personality. The theoretical and methodological basis of the study is the concept of a close relationship between the physical and mental development of the individual. According to secondary research, there is a close relationship between an individual's success in sports activities and his socio-psychological characteristics.

Key words: weightlifter, athlete, personality development, sport, weightlifting, health, sports activity.

Introduction. Today, the relevance of the problem of addressing physical culture and sports in general, and weightlifting in particular, is determined by the fact that since antiquity they have served as a means of promoting health, physical development, training the body and spirit, as well as personality development [3, 5, 6]. And genuine interest in the personal development of an athlete "permeates all spheres of human existence, including sports activity," because "involvement in sports contributes to the development of self-regulation skills, especially flexibility and independence" of the individual [1, 2, 4].

In the state standard for sports, weightlifting indicates the highest level of importance for the development of speed and strength abilities, optimal motor activity and the development of the athlete's personality as a whole [9, 11]. Indeed, a concentrated expression of a person's motor activity, as well as the formation of

physical, mental and social health, is physical culture, sports and strength training [7, 8].

A characteristic feature of the sports activity of a weightlifter is the desire for sports excellence, which follows from the concept of a close relationship between the physical and mental development of the individual. The basic theoretical and methodological provisions of this concept are reflected in fundamental works and studies [10, 12, 13]. Among them is the provision on the integrity of human development, his unity as an organism and personality, a subject of social activity, activity and individuality.

The personality of an athlete in the light of this approach is considered as a holistic formation that reflects the social essence of the conscious subject of sports activity, the emerging personal characteristics and the interpersonal relationships that arise here [16].

There are a considerable number of Uzbek and foreign works authors devoted to “weightlifting” technologies and weightlifting as the most important component of various types of physical culture and sports, contributing to the development of the athlete’s personality, including: D. G. Yusupov, L. S. Davronov, Mukhamedyarov, Y. Hartmann.

The attitude towards health and body as a value among modern young people in the framework of various weightlifting exercises has different aspects. The main ones that stimulate increased attention to the body and the desire to change it for the better through weightlifting training are, first of all, aesthetic (beauty, body relief); physical (strength, endurance); physiological (health, good psychosomatic well-being) [14].

One of the effective means of shaping the body and developing the personal qualities of an athlete is weightlifting. In Western countries, weightlifting is a sociocultural complex that includes traditional elements for this complex, starting with its own philosophy and ending with trade (business). At the same time, the goal setting in relation to weightlifting (within the framework of elite sports) - the unity

of strength, beauty (beautiful sports form) and health - is carefully supported by all athletes and serves as a system-forming factor in the existence of this complex [7, 15].

Speaking about the influence of weightlifting on the development of a person's motor qualities, domestic researchers highlight basic weightlifting exercises (squats, bench press, deadlift) and point to the important fact that when doing weightlifting, the load of strength exercises must necessarily correspond to physical, physiological and psychosomatic capabilities of the individual, also contributing to the development of the athlete's personal qualities. In this regard, the power load should "be selected in accordance with the goals and objectives: light weight (40-60% of the maximum); average weight (60-80% of maximum); heavy weight (from 80 to 100%)" [8].

A distinctive feature of weightlifting is characterized by the manifestation of speed-strength abilities of maximum power and complex coordination techniques. Weightlifting is based on strength training as an integral part of various types of physical culture and sports [17, 18]. Through strength training you can:

- firstly, increase muscle mass, increase muscle elasticity, reduce excess fat deposits, improve posture, gain excellent athletic shape (figure), and also increase the level of such important physical qualities of an athlete's personality as strength, flexibility, speed and endurance;
- secondly, targeted strength and weightlifting training is an important factor in the development of an athlete's personality, contributing to the readiness to overcome various difficulties and the formation of persistent, strong-willed character traits: determination, perseverance, dedication, courage, initiative, responsibility and discipline.

As foreign researchers J. Hartmann and H. Tünnemann emphasize, weightlifting, being a factor in the development of an athlete's personality, allows one to receive moral and physical pleasure from training in a team, from learning new exercises and using innovative technologies within the framework of strength

training, and together with this growth The achieved results not only increase the need for regular and systematic training, but also create a stable psycho-emotional state of the individual and form willpower.

Researcher N. N. Mukhamedyarov emphasizes that “strength sports involve concentration of attention, intellectual and volitional tension, which contributes to the formation and development of thinking” of the personality of a young athlete. After conducting research, N. N. Mukhamedyarov identifies the following qualities of sports thinking: speed, flexibility, criticality, independence, depth, creativity. At the same time, the author is convinced that the combination of such qualities shapes the athlete’s personality, contributes to the formation and development of intellectual abilities necessary in sports activities and in ordinary everyday life in society.

When performing strength exercises, there is an enhanced development of neural networks, which contributes to the development of many brain structures responsible not only for the mental sphere, but also for cognitive, imaginative, mnemonic and volitional, which ultimately leads to the holistic and full development of the athlete’s personality [19].

Based on the opinions of researchers, it follows that there is a close relationship between the success of an individual in sports activities and his socio-psychological characteristics. A successful athlete has well-developed volitional personality traits (persistence and self-control), is endowed with leadership qualities (associated with self-confidence, minimal dependence on external factors), achievement motivation, as well as a tendency to dominate (competition), moderate aggressiveness, allowing one to overcome obstacles on the way to sports weightlifting achievements [20].

Some researchers devoted their research to the study of gender characteristics of the personal qualities of athletes involved in weightlifting, which, in their opinion, have not been sufficiently studied. Scientists have come to the interesting conclusion that there are certain gender differences. Thus, women in power loads demonstrate

ambivalent (dual) behavioral strategies: they are forced to resort to the implementation of a masculine type of behavior in order to defend their position in sports activities, but at the same time they retain specifically feminine character traits and behavior patterns. Ambivalence in the personality traits and behavior of female weightlifters, according to the conclusions of the above authors, proves their tendency to androgenism. Unlike women, male weightlifters demonstrate masculine behavior that is comfortable for them, “clearly aware of its masculine orientation, which is associated with an increase in the level of expression of personal qualities necessary for achievement: internality in the field of achievement, the field of industrial relations, modeling, planning and motivation to success” [9].

Conclusions. Numerous studies indicate that “training with dosed weights in childhood and adolescence does not lead to deterioration of health and growth retardation,” on the contrary, it has a beneficial effect on the comprehensive physical, mental and social development and formation of the athlete’s personality. Thus, with the help of weightlifting exercises, as a factor in personality development, it is possible not only to change the functional state of the athlete’s body and regulate it in a targeted manner, but also to cause progressive adaptive changes in his physical, mental and social spheres, thereby contributing to the full and multifaceted formation of personality athlete.

References:

1. Alikulovich, M. K., & Yuldashevich, T. D. (2020). Development of physical training skills and formation of willpower qualities in extracurricular activities. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences* Vol, 8(3), 2021.
2. Alikulovich, M. K. (2022, October). The significance of psychological preparation of young swimmers. In *Proceedings of International Conference on Scientific Research in Natural and Social Sciences* (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 84-88).

3. Alikulovich, M. K. (2022). Mobile Games on the Water as a Means of Developing the Physical Qualities of School Children. *European Multidisciplinary Journal of Modern Science*, 4, 783-786.
4. Maxkamovich, A. Y., & Abdukahorovich, S. K. (2019). Modern approaches to the content of physical education of schoolchildren in the continuing education system. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences Vol*, 7(12).
5. Kholmuratov, F. H. (2023). Scientific and theoretical approaches to physical education in higher education institution. *Modern Scientific Research International Scientific Journal*, 1(8), 166-171.
6. Kholmuratov, F. H. (2023). Training swimming techniques for young athletes. *Modern Scientific Research International Scientific Journal*, 1(8), 187-192.
7. Kholmuratov, F. H. (2024). Formation of motor skills by weightlifting in the process of physical education. *Modern Scientific Research International Scientific Journal*, 2(2), 311-316.
6. Turdimurodov Dilmurod Yuldashevich. (2023). Formation and development of volitional regulation in preschool children. *Modern Scientific Research International Scientific Journal*, 1(2), 33–40.
7. Turdimurodov, D. Y. (2021). Preschool period: pedagogical aspect of education of will in a child. *Current Research Journal of Pedagogics (2767-3278)*, 2(09), 47-51.
8. Turdimurodov, D. Y. (2021). Testing volitional qualities for students of high schools of secondary school. *The American Journal of Social Science and Education Innovations*, 3(03), 405-413.
9. Turdimurodov Dilmurod Yuldashevich. (2024). PSYCHOLOGICAL PREPARATION OF YOUNG BOXERS. *Spectrum Journal of Innovation, Reforms and Development*, 25, 93–97.

10. Абдуллаев, Я. М., & Турдимуродов, Д. Й. (2020). Ўсмир ёшдаги ўқувчиларда продромий сифатларни жисмоний тарбия воситалари орқали ривожлантириш. *Современное образование (Узбекистан)*, (9 (94)), 56-62.
11. Абдуллаев, Я. М., & Юлдашевич, Т. Д. (2020). Создание педагогических условий в формировании волевых качеств у учеников начальных классов. In *Colloquium-journal* (No. 24 (76), pp. 36-38). Голопристанський міськрайонний центр зайнятості.
12. Менгликулов, Х. (2023). Harakatli o'yinlar orqali 14-15 yoshli suzuvchilarning jismoniy sifatlarini rivojlantirish. *Ижтимоий-гуманитар фанларнинг долзарб муаммолари/Актуальные проблемы социально-гуманитарных наук/Actual Problems of Humanities and Social Sciences.*, 3(3), 230-236.
13. Менгликулов, Х. А. (2022). Ёш сузувчиларни ўргатишнинг бошланғич bosqichida танловнинг назарий жиҳатлари. *Современное образование (Узбекистан)*, (8 (117)), 55-59.
14. Саттарова, Б., & Холмуродов, Ф. Х. (2021). Оценка знаний студентов-иностранцев. *Инновации в педагогике и психологии*, 4(7).
15. Турдимуродов, Д. (2023). Yuqori sinf o'quvchilarida qat'iyatlilik sifatini jismoniy tarbiya darslarida tarbiyalash. *Ижтимоий-гуманитар фанларнинг долзарб муаммолари/Актуальные проблемы социально-гуманитарных наук/Actual Problems of Humanities and Social Sciences.*, 3(3), 218-223.
16. Турдимуродов, Д. (2024). Sport mashg'ulotlari jarayonida pedagogik nazoratning ahamiyati. *Ижтимоий-гуманитар фанларнинг долзарб муаммолари/Актуальные проблемы социально-гуманитарных наук/Actual Problems of Humanities and Social Sciences.*, 4(4).
17. Холмуродов, Ф. Х. (2020). Педагогические и методические подходы в обучении сложным техническим приемам юных волейболистов. *Вопросы педагогики*, (5-2), 427-431.

18. Холмуродов, Ф. Х. (2016). Организация и методика физического воспитания детей в разных возрастных группах. *Вестник современной науки*, (6-2), 137-140.

19. Холмуродов, Ф. Х. (2016). Методические принципы физического воспитания и их реализации в процессе занятий физическими упражнениями. *Вестник современной науки*, (6-2), 134-136.